

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPIRATORY ALLERGIES IN THE PEDIATRIC POPULATION OF THE ARAL SEA REGION

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Abstract. *In recent decades, there has been a significant increase in the incidence of respiratory allergies, such as bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis, pollinosis, chronic tonsillitis, and adenoid diseases, often combined with allergic dermatitis, the prevalence of which has increased more than threefold. Respiratory allergies are a group of respiratory diseases that can affect the nose and sinuses, larynx, trachea, bronchi, and lungs.*

Over the past five years, there has been a significant increase in the percentage of children in the Republic of Karakalpakstan seeking medical help for the first time due to respiratory allergies. A correlation analysis of allergic morbidity with environmental indicators was conducted. It was found that the greatest impact on the frequency of allergic pathology is exerted by the levels of air and drinking water pollution.

Keywords: *children, respiratory allergies, allergic diseases, environmental factors, Pre-Aral region.*

Аннотация. *В последние десятилетия отмечается значительный рост заболеваемости респираторными аллергиями, такими как бронхиальная астма, аллергический ринит, поллинозы, хронические заболевания миндалин и аденоидов и их сочетании аллергодерматозами, уровень которых увеличился более чем в 3 раза. Респираторные аллергии — это группа заболеваний органов дыхания, которые могут затрагивать нос и придаточные пазухи, гортань, трахею, бронхи и лёгкие.*

За последние 5 лет в РК произошло значительное увеличение процента детей, обратившихся впервые за медицинской помощью из-за аллергических заболеваний органов дыхания. Была проведена корреляционный анализ аллергической заболеваемости с показателями окружающей среды. Выявлено что, наибольшее влияние на частоту аллергической патологии оказывает уровень загрязнения воздуха и питьевой воды.

Ключевые слова: *дети, респираторные аллергии, аллергические заболевания, экологические факторы, регион Приаралья.*

Relevance

Over the past two decades, there has been an increase in cases of allergic diseases, especially among children. Most researchers associate this rise with environmental pollution from chemical substances, including pollution of air, water, and soil. According to WHO experts, environmental factors account for more than 20% of causes negatively impacting human health [1, 4].

Studies show that chemical concentrations exceeding permissible levels have been detected in the air, drinking water, and soil of the Aral Sea region. The desiccation of the Aral Sea has created a vast salt desert that periodically releases large amounts of dust into the atmosphere, containing salts, pesticides, and other harmful substances. When these particles enter the respiratory tract, they irritate the mucous membranes and may trigger allergic reactions [3, 5].

Allergic diseases, particularly respiratory tract disorders, are closely linked to environmental factors, as the phenotypic expression of hereditary predispositions is influenced by the surrounding environment. For instance, bronchial asthma, especially in children, is a sensitive indicator of air pollution [4, 11]. The rise in respiratory allergies observed in recent years is largely attributed to environmental contamination with xenobiotics [2, 14].

The hot, dry climate and sharp seasonal temperature fluctuations contribute to frequent respiratory diseases, further aggravated by low air humidity and high dust concentration. These factors increase the likelihood of respiratory allergies and complicate their progression. The concentration of airborne pollutants depends on climatic and geographic conditions [10, 13]. Against the backdrop of general environmental issues, the region suffers from high levels of atmospheric pollution due to the erosion of salt deposits. Inhalation of polluted air leads to respiratory tract damage and heightened sensitivity to allergens, which, in turn, increases the risk of respiratory allergic diseases in children [8, 12].

These substances can cause bronchoconstriction, temporarily increase bronchial hyperreactivity, induce sensitization, and exert a direct toxic effect on the respiratory epithelium [2, 9].

Assessing the health status, disease prevalence, and risk factors in the pediatric population is crucial for every region to enable health authorities to make informed decisions regarding the organization of preventive and therapeutic care for the population. Developing effective preventive measures is impossible without analyzing reliable data on the prevalence of allergic diseases and the factors contributing to their development. All of this underscores the relevance of conducting this study.

The aim of this study is to assess the prevalence and clinical characteristics of respiratory allergic diseases in children in the Aral Sea region.

Epidemiological studies indicate that respiratory allergies are among the most common types of diseases in children in the Aral Sea region. Research data show that the prevalence of bronchial asthma and allergic rhinitis in this region is significantly higher than in other areas with a more favorable ecology. Specifically, in areas most affected by salt dust, a higher number of bronchial asthma cases have been recorded, with children suffering from more severe clinical forms of the disease, often requiring frequent hospitalizations [1, 7].

In 2022, the respiratory disease incidence rate in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (RK) reached 302.6 cases per 1,000 people among adults, 711.4 among adolescents, and 1,067.5 among children. The primary incidence of chronic bronchitis in adults doubled compared to 2018. Chronic respiratory diseases are becoming increasingly common among children and adolescents. The prevalence of bronchial asthma increased by 1.4 times among adults and by 37% among adolescents. In 2022, newly diagnosed cases of chronic tonsillitis and adenoid diseases increased by 46.2% in children and by 32% in adolescents compared to 2018.

The structure of disease prevalence among the pediatric population in RK is characterized by a predominance of allergic diseases. In recent decades, there has been a significant rise in respiratory allergies, such as bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis, and pollinosis, often combined with allergic dermatitis, with rates having increased more than threefold [1, 2, 7]. Respiratory allergies comprise a group of respiratory diseases that may affect the nose and sinuses, larynx, trachea, bronchi, and lungs. They develop due to the activation of allergic immunological mechanisms. This process is driven by the interaction of allergens with the body's immune response, regulated by genetic factors and hormonal changes.

The incidence of allergic pathology in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (RK) has increased 3.2 times over the past 10 years, with allergic rhinitis (AR) rising 3.4 times, pollinosis (P) 2.8 times, and atopic dermatitis (AD) 2.3 times. Therefore, issues of prevention, effective treatment, and improving the quality of life for patients are pressing for most countries, including Karakalpakstan.

Respiratory allergic diseases present as year-round and seasonal rhinitis as well as bronchial asthma. In recent years, the proportion of respiratory pathologies in the structure of allergic diseases has increased [6], including allergic rhinitis, as confirmed by analysis of disease incidence data.

In Karakalpakstan, over the past five years, the number of children visiting clinics for allergic rhinitis has risen significantly: by 15.4% in 2023, which is twice the 2018 level. Clinical manifestations of respiratory allergic diseases in children in the Aral Sea region are characterized by prolonged periods of exacerbation, difficulty breathing, chronic cough, frequent colds, often complicated by bacterial infections. Children with allergies in this region are also prone to developing severe forms of atopic dermatitis, potentially indicating a systemic allergic response.

From 2018 to 2023, the proportion of children with respiratory allergies combined with atopic dermatitis under medical supervision in RK increased by 1.3 times. The incidence rate rose by 1.6 times, indicating a continuing rise in respiratory allergies among children. Of the total number of children diagnosed with allergic pathology, 66.5% had isolated forms of allergic diseases: atopic dermatitis in 27.5%, bronchial asthma in 26.4%, and seasonal allergic rhinitis in 12.6% of children. An analysis of age-related features of allergic diseases in children revealed a clear trend in the variation of clinical manifestations with age. In children under three years old, atopic dermatitis is most common; up to five years, both atopic dermatitis and bronchial asthma are prevalent. At ages 6-7, a combination of atopic dermatitis and bronchial asthma is frequently observed, and from seven years onward, isolated seasonal allergic rhinitis and its combination with bronchial asthma are more commonly diagnosed.

An analysis was conducted on the frequency of allergic diseases in children in RK, characterized by particularly adverse environmental conditions. Health monitoring of children is carried out in parallel with monitoring of air pollution levels, allowing for correlation between disease incidence data and environmental conditions. A correlation analysis was performed between allergic disease rates and environmental indicators. It was found that there is a varying degree of association between these indicators. Air pollution has the most significant impact on allergy incidence: the correlation coefficient was $r=0.62$ for patients with bronchial asthma, $r=0.54$ for those with allergic rhinitis, and $r=0.47$ for those with atopic dermatitis. Water pollution also correlates with the frequency of atopic dermatitis ($r=0.45$) and, to a lesser extent, bronchial asthma ($r=0.38$). Cohort studies are conducted to assess the long-term impact of environmental factors on allergy development, tracking the health dynamics and symptom changes over time in children.

Our research shows high levels of allergic disease prevalence, primarily bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis, and atopic dermatitis, alongside identified correlations between allergic diseases and environmental pollution.

Conclusion. The epidemiological characteristics of respiratory allergies in the pediatric population of the Aral Sea region indicate the need for a comprehensive approach to the study and prevention of these diseases. Given the severe environmental situation, the region requires special attention to improving medical care, monitoring air pollution, and implementing educational programs for the population.

The system of preventive and therapeutic measures for children with allergic conditions in ecologically unfavorable areas should include improving sanitary and hygienic conditions, rehabilitating children considering the combined effects of pollution, and organizing long-term monitoring of children's health.

Enhancing environmental conditions and improving the quality of diagnostics will significantly reduce the incidence of respiratory allergies among children and improve the overall health of the younger generation in the Aral Sea region.

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